

CM4AI FAIRSCAPE Portal Requirements

A Cell Maps for Artificial Intelligence Standards Module Deliverable

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Abstract

This document describes requirements for a data access portal for data held in the Cell Maps for Artificial Intelligence (CM4AI) FAIRSCAPE instance. CM4AI is a Data Generation project in the NIH Bridge2AI program. The FAIRSCAPE CM4AI Data Access portal will be the central access portal for cataloged FAIR CM4AI metadata on software, datasets, and computations for all Bridge2AI participants and AI end users. It will enable CM4AI digital objects to be tracked, objects to be requested, and requests assessed and tracked. It may also eventually play a role in providing assessment of outcomes of use..

1 Introduction

The Cell Maps for Artificial Intelligence (CM4AI) project, a data generation project in the NIH Bridge2AI program, will generate comprehensively FAIR data and software [1, 2] on the experimentally and computationally determined architecture of select human cell lines for use by the biomedical AI community. To support appropriate and informed use it will provide users with deep provenance graphs on these digital objects, and a comprehensive CM4AI Data Dictionary [3]. CM4AI FAIR digital objects will be processed, published, and released, via a FAIRSCAPE [4,5,6] instance and closely associated provenance-tracking Evidence Graph Ontology [7,8], developed by the Standards module, in collaboration with the Data Acquisition and Tools Modules.

To provide accessibility to released datasets and software, and in the future, to full replication packages; and to catalog their versions and status, a web portal is required, with specific requirements determined by the goals and structure of CM4AI.

Requirements for this portal were determined by careful review of the FAIR data and software literature; the CM4AI Module Statements of Work for each module; the CM4AI Data Dictionary Requirements; and by in-depth discussions conducted between team members of CM4AI Tools and Standards Modules during September 2022. Additional comments were sought from Module leads of Data Acquisition and Teaming Modules, with final approval by the CM3AI Contact Principal Investigator.

2 Personas and Use Cases

2.1 CM4AI, Bridge Center, NIH Staff, and Other Bridge2AI Participants

These personas, all of them participants in developing, integrating, and / or funding CM4AI and other Bridge2AI Data Generation Projects, will interact with the CM4AI FAIRSCAPE portal. This portal will serve as a repository of catalog metadata about CM4AI digital objects. It will be used to track project progress and completion status, to assess functionality, to access metadata, to explore interoperability options, and to request digital objects for download and use.

These participants will require access to the CM4AI Data Dictionary, its instantiated metadata, its released and in-development datasets, and to all other digital objects produced by the project. This digital content must be available in conveniently navigable and searchable form, including searchability by object name, description, status, availability, etc., including a global listing of all objects in the project regardless of status. We note that ultimately “status” may encompass computational status, i.e. in-process computations.

Furthermore, some, or all, of these participant personas will want to track the requests for digital objects to assess project impact, downstream use, and compliance with licensing and other terms of use requirements. This suggests that *Biomedical AI Researchers* (2.2 below) may need to register unique identifying attributes, such as ORCIDs, with the portal, to request datasets.

2.2 *Biomedical AI Researchers*

This group of users is the ultimate target audience and consumer of CM4AI, constituting its *raison d'être*. Biomedical AI users will interact with the CM4AI FAIRSCAPE dataset portal to determine what datasets are available, in what versions, and with what availability and license terms; and to request them. As noted above it will be important to track usage and identify users, user outcomes, and products of use.

3 Portal Requirements

3.1 *Human Accessibility on the Web*

The FAIRSCAPE portal information must be available on the Web for widest human accessibility and utility to both technical and non-technical users.

3.2 *Metadata only – digital content held separately*

FAIR data and software requirements specify that data and metadata are to be held separately; that is, a call to an http- or https-resolvable persistent identifier resolves to the metadata, and after some further processing occurs by the calling agents (which may or may not be minimal), the digital content may be resolved via the content URL, which is held as a metadata element.

3.3 *Read only access*

The FAIRSCAPE portal component will provide read-only access to metadata and will not provide the ability to instantiate or modify any CM4AI component.

3.4 *Access by specific request with documentation*

Data will not be downloaded without requestors filling out forms and (conceivably) also making certain commitments to NIH. For example, it is clearly desirable that requestors identify themselves and their institutions so that product use can be tracked. It may also be desirable to require users to report publications, datasets, and software developed based on CM4AI products. Users should be required to register using verifiable unique credentials such as an ORCID, and their identities should be tracked for program metrics and to encourage integration, articulation, and organized collaboration of downstream artifacts with the Bridge2AI program.

Other download criteria may be needed; but minimally a usage tracking capability is necessary.

3.5 *Terms of use*

The FAIRSCAPE portal will provide formal licensing and terms of use applicable to each dataset or software product it catalogs.

3.6 *Metadata accessed via FAIRSCAPE APIs*

All metadata vended through the portal will be accessed via the documented FAIRSCAPE APIs and not through any secondary means.

3.7 *Metadata structure and content in human and machine-readable form.*

Metadata structure and content will be provided in human- and machine-readable form, as defined in the CM4AI Data Dictionary.

3.8 *Content may be held in various and potentially replicated locations.*

Because data will be processed at distinct locations – at the University of California San Diego (UCSD), University of California San Francisco (UCSF), Stanford, and University of Virginia (UVA) – and the digital objects themselves may be large, digital content may or may not be replicated across locations, while metadata will be held centrally in FAIRSCAPE.

3.9 *Digital objects may be published and held in various long-term repositories.*

To make CM4AI digital objects robustly accessible over longer periods of time, and readily findable by researchers not directly associated and/or aware of the Bridge2AI program, digital objects may additionally be published in various other established (i.e., demonstrably funded for longer than the funding period of Bridge2AI) repositories, or in relevant domain-specific repositories. Metadata will continue to be cataloged and available in the FAIRSCAPE portal, with multiple links to download locations.

3.10 *Design and management by Data Acquisition, Tools and Standards modules.*

The portal will be intimately aligned with the development outputs of the CM4AI Data Acquisition, Tools and Standards modules, and therefore design and content management will be by the PIs of these modules in consultation with the Teaming module.

4 **Conclusion**

This document has outlined the base requirement for the CM4AI FAIRSCAPE portal component, which will provide a metadata catalog and request mechanism for the CM4AI-produced digital objects and associated metadata descriptions.

References

1. Wilkinson, M.D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I.J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A., Blomberg, N., Boiten, J.-W., da Silva Santos, L.B., Bourne, P.E., Bouwman, J., Brookes, A.J., Clark, T., Crosas, M., Dillo, I., Dumon, O., Edmunds, S., Evelo, C.T., Finkers, R., Gonzalez-Beltran, A., Gray, A.J.G., Groth, P., Goble, C., Grethe, J.S., Heringa, J., 't Hoen, P.A.C., Hooft, R., Kuhn, T., Kok, R., Kok, J., Lusher, S.J., Martone, M.E., Mons, A., Packer, A.L., Persson, B., Rocca-Serra, P., Roos, M., van Schaik, R., Sansone, S.-A., Schultes, E., Sengstag, T., Slater, T., Strawn, G., Swertz, M.A., Thompson, M., van der Lei, J., van Mulligen, E., Velterop, J., Waagmeester, A., Wittenburg, P., Wolstencroft, K., Zhao, J., Mons, B.: The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data*. 3, 160018 (2016).
2. Chue Hong, N.P., Katz, D.S., Barker, M., Lamprecht, A.-L., Martinez, C., Psomopoulos, F.E., Harrow, J., Castro, L.J., Gruenpeter, M., Martinez, P.A., Honeyman, T.: FAIR Principles for Research Software (FAIR4RS Principles). (2021). <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00065>.
3. Clark T, Al Manir S, Chen J, Churas C, Jeffery E, Levinson MA, Pratt DE, Ratcliffe S, Sheynkman S. 2022. CM4AI Data Dictionary Requirements, version 1.0. BioRxiv [in press].

4. Levinson, M.A., Niestroy, J., Manir, S.A., Fairchild, K., Lake, D.E., Moorman, J.R., Clark, T.: FAIRSCAPE: A Framework for FAIR and Reproducible Biomedical Analytics. *Neuroinformatics*. (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12021-021-09529-4>.
5. Niestroy, J., Cullen, T., Fulcher, B.D.: Fairscape/hctsa-py: HCTSA Python (Version 1.0), <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4508644>, (2020).
6. Niestroy, J.C., Moorman, J.R., Levinson, M.A., Manir, S.A., Clark, T.W., Fairchild, K.D., Lake, D.E.: Discovery of signatures of fatal neonatal illness in vital signs using highly comparative time-series analysis. *npj Digit. Med.* 5, 6 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-021-00551-z>.
7. Al Manir, S., Niestroy, J., Levinson, M.A., Clark, T.: Evidence Graphs: Supporting Transparent and FAIR Computation, with Defeasible Reasoning on Data, Methods, and Results. In: Glavic, B., Braganholo, V., and Koop, D. (eds.) *Provenance and Annotation of Data and Processes*. pp. 39–50. Springer International Publishing, Cham (2021). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-80960-7_3.
8. Al Manir, S., Niestroy, J., Levinson, M., Clark, T.: EVI: The Evidence Graph Ontology, OWL 2 Vocabulary, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4630931>, (2021).